

Questionnaire for Flood Vulnerability

The following questionnaire is a crucial phase of this study which has as main object the development of an integrated vulnerability tool addressing flood risk, seismic risk, landslide risk and building energy efficiency.

This tool should be able to indicate what the overall vulnerability of a building is, for the purpose of more effective management of interventions.

The developed methodology that can be valid for:

- residential building typology present in Algeria, and in particular for the area of the Wadi Abiod Valley;
- buildings with features similar to the one present in Algeria located in areas of the Globe subject to seismic, flood, and landslide risks, where targeted interventions for energy efficiency need to be implemented.

For the purpose of this assessment, individual vulnerabilities (called V_S , V_F , V_L , V_E in the diagram below) will first be assessed.

At the preliminary stage of the study, based on the relevant literature, the main factors affecting individual vulnerabilities toward seismic, flood, landslide risks and energy efficiency were identified. Then, these factors have been expertly grouped into categories.

With this questionnaire, we ask you, as experts, to give a weight to the individual vulnerability factors and categories that is representative of the factor or category importance in defining the total vulnerability of the building.

For clarity, the diagram below summarizes the steps identified for the individual vulnerability assessment.

Once the weights to each category and factor have been determined, the weight of the individual factor will be given by the product of the weight of the category and the weight of the factor within that category.

In particular, the individual vulnerability of the building (V_S , V_F , V_L , V_E) will be given by the following formula:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n P_i * \sum_{j=1}^m p_{i,j} * v_{i,j}$$

Where:

- P_i is the weight of the category i
- $p_{i,j}$ is the weight of the factor j within category i
- $v_{i,j}$ is the value of the factor j within category i (appropriately reclassified on a scale from 0 to 1)
- n is the total number of categories.
- m is the total number of factors within each category

Finally, the individual vulnerabilities for each risk will be integrated based on their respective hazards. This integration will allow for a comprehensive understanding of the building's overall vulnerability profile. The result can be used by decision-makers to prioritize mitigation efforts and allocate resources effectively to enhance the resilience of the building against various hazards.

Instructions for Questionnaire Completion

In what follows, you will first be provided with a description of the individual categories and the related factors identified for your risk. Then, you will be provided with an outline where you can provide your judgment and any comments and/or suggestions.

The following steps are recommended for completing the questionnaire:

1. First read the entire questionnaire, without thinking about assigning any values. This step serves to gain an overview of the problem in all its components.
2. Carefully reread the definitions of categories and factors.
3. Only then to associate a weight with each category (P_i), such that the sum of the category weights is equal to 1.
4. Next, we ask you to associate a weight ($p_{i,j}$) to the factors contained in each category, according to the criterion that within each category the sum of the weights should be equal to 1.

Note: in the COMMENTS section you should enter reason for choosing a weight value, whereas, in the SUGGESTIONS section you should enter eventual suggestions of any kind, including changes that you deem necessary (e.g., other factors to be considered, factors to be neglected, how the define the factor, etc...).

IT IS IMPORTANT THAT ANY CHOICES OR COMMENTS BE ARGUED, SO THAT THIS INFORMATION CAN BE PROVIDED TO THE POOL OF EXPERTS INVOLVED, WHO MAY

MODIFY OR CONFIRM THEIR INITIAL JUDGMENT, AT A SECOND STAGE OF THE INVESTIGATION.

FLOOD VULNERABILITY INDEX

Category 1: Structural type and construction materials

This category includes all factors related to the structural characteristics (year of construction, construction type and material) and cladding materials of the building. This category then goes to assess what the building's propensity for physical damage is.

Weight Category 1 (P1)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

Category 2: Propensity to flooding.

This category includes all those features that may or may not favor the entry of water into the building such as the presence of basement floors or the number of openings present in the lower floors.

Weight Category 2 (P2)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

Category 3: Location of facilities

The following category goes to define what the location (and type) of the plumbing, heating, and air conditioning system is.

Weight Category 3 (P3)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

Category 1: Structural type and construction materials

- **Year of construction**

The year of construction factor refers to the year of completion. While newer buildings may have inherent advantages in terms of compliance with modern building codes and standards, older buildings can still be retrofitted or upgraded to enhance flood resilience.

Weight Factor 1 (p ₁₁)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

- **Residential type**

Residential types are distinguished based on the way in which the individual units are grouped together. According to building typology, variations occur in the organization of common areas, the distribution of installations, as well as the number of floors and materials used.

Weight Factor 2 (p ₁₂)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

- **Construction material**

The construction material refers to the material of the load-bearing structure, which can be concrete, masonry, stone, wood, etc... The vulnerability associated to different construction materials increases with the propensity of the material itself to be damaged by the action of water.

Weight Factor 3 (p ₁₃)	
Comments	

Suggestions	
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- **Exterior wall cladding**

There are different cladding materials for external walls, such as plaster, exposed brick or stone facade, stoneware, etc...

Weight Factor 4 (p14)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

- **Interior wall material**

The material of internal walls refers to the material of non-load-bearing partition structures.

Weight Factor 5 (p15)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

- **Interior wall cladding**

There are different cladding materials for internal walls such as ceramic, plaster, paper, etc...

Weight Factor 6 (p16)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

- **Floor materials**

There are different materials that can make up the floorings of a building such as cement, stone, moquette, etc...

Weight Factor 7 (p ₁₇)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

Category 2: Propensity to flooding.

- **Number of floors**
This means the number of floors above ground.

Weight Factor 1 (p ₂₁)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

- **Presence of basement floors**
Basement floors are the floors located in the underground level of a building.

Weight Factor 2 (p ₂₂)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

- **Floodable floor openings**
Floodable floor openings can be defined as openings or apertures in a building's structure, such as windows or doors which facilitate water ingress during flooding events.

Weight Factor 3 (p23)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

- **Presence of check valves**

This factor indicates the presence or absence of non-return valves serving the hydraulic system.

Weight Factor 4 (p24)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

Category 3: Location of facilities

- **Electrical system position**

With this factor, it is required to define the elevation relative to the floor of the control cabinet, so that it can be understood whether it is above or below the floodproof level.

Weight Factor 1 (p31)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

- **Plumbing system position**

This factor is used to define the floor level of the plumbing system so that it can be understood whether it is above or below the flood level.

Weight Factor 2 (p32)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

- **Thermal system position**

With this factor, we are asked to define the height above the floor of the heating system (e.g., boiler), so that we can understand whether it is above or below the floodable level.

Weight Factor 3 (p33)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

- **Heating system type**

The heating system is taken into account in defining the overall vulnerability to floods, considering the cost associated with different types of heating systems.

Weight Factor 4 (p34)	
Comments	
Suggestions	

- **Emission terminals**

By emission terminals we mean the type of terminal used to emit heat into the room such as radiators and thermal convectors.

Weight Factor 5 (p35)	
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Comments	
Suggestions	